

Monastery of Panagia (Virgin) Soumela

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Religious Group, Byzantine, Trebizond, Monastery, Church, Greek, Byzantine, Language, Religious Place, Monument, Orthodoxy

The Imperial, Patriarchal and Stauropegial Monastery of Panagia Soumela (meaning "of black (mountain)" in Greek) is located on the western slopes of Mount Melas, in the Maçka district of Trebizond province in modern Turkey. The tradition places its foundation to the 4th century and attributes its establishment to two Athenian monks, Barnabas and Sophronios, who supposedly discovered in a cave an icon of the Virgin, said to have been painted by Saint Luke. During its long history, the Monastery was destroyed and restored several times. During the 6th century, it was restored and enlarged by the Byzantine general Belissarius at the behest of emperor Justinian. It reached its current form in the 13th century, but it prospered during the reign of Alexios III Komnenos (1349-1390) who has restored the Monastery between 1360 and 1365 and endowed it with hereditary lands and dependents, listed in the chrysobull issued in 1364. Moreover, he exempted the Monastery from all taxes (except for one biannual tax), while it restored to it the paroikoi (serfs), illegally taken from it. During the reigns of subsequent princes and rulers, Soumela gained further wealth from imperial grants. After the conquest of Trebizond by Sultan Mehmed II in 1461, the Monastery was granted his protection and given rights and privileges, which were subsequently renewed. Following the exchange of Greek and Turkish population (treaty of Lausanne) in 1923, Soumela Monastery was abandoned. In 1930 its wooden parts were destroyed by fire and in the following years other parts were damaged and pillaged. Some of its relics and treasures were transferred to the homonymous new Monastery founded in 1930 on Mount Vermion near Naousa, in Macedonia, Greece. The Monastery is currently a museum open to visitors. On the feast of the Dormition of the Theotokos (15 August) in 2010, Orthodox divine liturgy by the Oecumenical Patriarch was allowed to take place at the Monastery. The main grotto church (katholikon) is surrounded by nine chapels. In the 1970s another frescoed chapel was discovered to the north of the monastic complex. Its frescoes were dated to the 12th century. The frescoes of the katholikon date from the 12th to the 18th century. The oldest frescoes of the entire monastic complex of Soumela are the two medallions with the Virgin and Christ on the north side and a depiction of Archangel Gabriel on the south side of the ceiling. The iconographic programme contains as well portraits of the Trapezuntine emperors Alexios III and Emmanuel III Komnenos (east part of the south wall), most probably painted in the very beginning of the 15th century. Most of the frescoes that decorate the monastic complex date after 1461 and they belong to four different phases (i. 16th century; ii. 1710; iii. 1732; 18th century). Only the following four out of the nine chapels have painted decoration: i. chapel to the east of the main church; ii. chapel partially carved into the rock, behind the newer structure; iii. chapel above the main church; and, iv. chapel to the east of the destroyed bell tower. The Monastery of Panagia Soumela was submitted as a possible UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2000 and is currently listed on the Tentative list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites.

Date Range: 375 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Trebizond

Region tags: Turkey, Byzantium, Trebizond

Mount Melas, Maçka district, Trebizond province, modern Turkey

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Other [specify]: The monastic complex is nestled in a steep cliff at an altitude of about 1,200 metres facing the Altindere valley

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

– Canyon

– Rock face

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: All the above

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was destroyed and repaired or rebuilt many times throughout its history

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

– As the result of pillage

– Other [specify]: Following the exchange of Greek and Turkish population (treaty of Lausanne) in 1923 the Monastery was abandoned. In 1930 its wooden parts were destroyed by fire and in the following years other parts were damaged and pillaged.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The Monastery was reconstructed many times.

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Monastery is dedicated to the Mother of God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Millet, G., and D. Talbot Rice. *Byzantine Painting at Trebizond*. London, 1936.

– Source 2: Kyriakides, E. *Ιστορία Της Παρά Την Τραπεζούντα Ιεράς Βασιλικής Σταυροπηγιακής Μονής Της Υπεραγίας Θεοτόκου Της Σουμελά*. Athens, 1898.

– Source 3: Meinardus, O. "The Panagia of Soumela: Tradition and History," *Orientalia suecana*, 19-20 (1970).

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Water feature

– Plantings

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.ehw.gr/l.aspx?id=5239>

– Source 1 Description: Ματζούκα, Μονή Παναγίας Σουμελά, Καθολικό, Ζωγραφικός Διάκοσμος

– Source 2 URL: <https://charlvarchive.org/Album/85>

– Source 2 Description: The Christian Architecture of the Levant

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.sumela.gov.tr/>

– Source 3 Description: Website of the Turkish government

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: However, the monastic complex has been the object of several restoration campaigns.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

–King or emperor

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
– Yes

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify
–Other [specify]: The Monastery was built at the place where an icon of the Virgin was found

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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Notes: However, the monastic complex has been the object of several restoration campaigns.

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- Canyon
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- Leveling of ground
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Structures Present

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A single structure

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↳ Worship:

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↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The Monastery was reconstructed many times.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Monastery is dedicated to the Mother of God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

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Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built at the place where an icon of the Virgin was found

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis and icons

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ the Son of God is depicted

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Judge, angels and demons are depicted in the scene of the Last Judgment. Angels, cherubim and seraphim are included in the rest of the scenes as well

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are peupling the various scenes that depict events from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The animals are included in the scenes from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints depicted

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

Notes: The decoration is not non-figural. There are however non-figural decorative elements

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

- ↳ Type
 - 'True' fresco
 - Secco

- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Icons depicting Saints, the Mother of God, Angels and Christ

- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No

- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: There is a composition of the Last Judgment

- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No

- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - No

- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
 - Notes: The inscriptions in byzantine and post-byzantine monuments and generally in Christian orthodox churches describe the scene or the persons depicted

- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No

- ↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The frescoes and walls of the Monastery bear evidence of the huge number of pilgrims that have visited it, for there are many graffiti scratched

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Notes: The katholikon (main church) of the Monastery is hierarchically more important than the other chapels

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim, seraphim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: There is an immense scene of the Last Judgment

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and different Saints

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Lives of Saints and the Mother of God

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The different phases of the painted decoration of the main church and the chapels follow the byzantine tradition of iconography

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Pigments and binding materials

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments, gold and silver mixtures and binders were used for the mural paintings of the main church and the adjacent chapels

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

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↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

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Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

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↳ On the outside:

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↳ On the inside:

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Notes: Iconostasis and icons

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A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

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– Yes

Notes: Christ the Son of God is depicted

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– Yes

Notes: The Judge, angels and demons are depicted in the scene of the Last Judgment. Angels, cherubim and seraphim are included in the rest of the scenes as well

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are peopling the various scenes that depict events from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

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– No

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– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

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Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Icons depicting Saints, the Mother of God, Angels and Christ

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a composition of the Last Judgment

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

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↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

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↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

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Notes: The inscriptions in byzantine and post-byzantine monuments and generally in Christian orthodox churches describe the scene or the persons depicted

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The frescoes and walls of the Monastery bear evidence of the huge number of pilgrims that have visited it, for there are many graffiti scratched

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

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– No

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and different Saints

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Lives of Saints and the Mother of God

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The different phases of the painted decoration of the main church and the chapels follow the byzantine tradition of iconography

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: The Oecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople celebrates the Divine Liturgy on August 15

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
–specify: Once per year, if authorised by the Turkish government

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims are coming to the Monastery to pray

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery's feast day is August 15, the Dormition of the Virgin Mary. The Turkish government allows that the Oecumenical Patriarch celebrates an Orthodox divine Liturgy on that day

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Oecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople is given authorisation to celebrate a Divine Liturgy on the feast day of the Monastery

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: At the katholikon (main grotto church) of the Monastery

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: August 15

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The persons present at the Divine Liturgy on August 15 are given special authorisation by the Turkish government

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown. Before the abandonment of the Monastery a lot more pilgrims were visiting the Monastery throughout the year

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for the preservation of the Monastery for the next generations

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Monastery is overlooked, preserved and restored by various specialists

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims are coming to the Monastery to pray

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The Oecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople celebrates the Divine Liturgy on August 15

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Once per year, if authorised by the Turkish government

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

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↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from candles or edible goods to valuable objects and financial donations

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for the preservation of the Monastery for the next generations

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

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– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Monastery is overlooked, preserved and restored by various specialists

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery's feast day is August 15, the Dormition of the Virgin Mary. The Turkish government allows that the Oecumenical Patriarch celebrates an Orthodox divine Liturgy on that day

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Oecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople is given authorisation to celebrate a Divine Liturgy on the feast day of the Monastery

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: At the katholikon (main grotto church) of the Monastery

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: August 15

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The persons present at the Divine Liturgy on August 15 are given special authorisation by the Turkish government

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown. Before the abandonment of the Monastery a lot more pilgrims were visiting the Monastery throughout the year

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: There are no monks currently living at the Monastery

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: A chrysobull dated to 1364 lists the properties of the Monastery and characterises the relations between the Monastery and its serfs

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery includes cells but there is not a monastic community living there

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery was endowed by byzantine emperors with hereditary lands and dependents. However, since the establishment of the Turkish state, the legal status of the monastery and its

economic resources are unknown

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is not currently used for the training of religious specialists. However, in the past it housed the Phrontisterion of Trapezous, a well-known Greek educational institution of the region

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Turkish government is currently in charge for the protection and restoration of the monument

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Notes: The Monastery was endowed by byzantine emperors with hereditary lands and dependents. However, since the establishment of the Turkish state, the legal status of the monastery and its economic resources are unknown

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: A chrysobull dated to 1364 lists the properties of the Monastery and characterises the relations between the Monastery and its serfs

Bibliography

General References

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